

A SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

A.1 Questionnaires

Table A1 presents the UES-SF items in their original order, grouped by subscales (Focused Attention, Perceived Usability, Aesthetic Elements, Reward Factor) to simplify direct comparison between post-VR and post-Kelly adaptations. Table A2 presents the PCY items in sequence for post-VR and post-Alex contexts, maintaining the original structure for clarity.

A.2 Storyboards

Figures A3 and A4 present the complete storyboard panels used in Study 2 for the two narrative interventions. Figure A3 shows Alex's biometric profiling scenario, and Figure A4 shows Kelly's overengagement scenario. Each storyboard consists of eight panels presented in fixed order and depicts a third-person narrative illustrating how the corresponding risk unfolds in a VR-related context.

The storyboards are used as static narrative stimuli and are shown in full here to support transparency, reproducibility, and interpretation of the results. They provide the visual and narrative material on which participants base their emotional, engagement, and risk perception judgments in Study 2.

Table A1: UES-SF items: original version, post-VR adaptation, post-Kelly adaptation.

ID	Original version	Post-VR adaptation	Post-Kelly adaptation
Focused Attention (FA)			
FA-S.1	I lost myself in this experience	I lost myself in this experience	Kelly lost herself in this experience
FA-S.2	The time I spent using Application X just slipped away	The time I spent using the VR application just slipped away	The time Kelly spent using the VR application just slipped away
FA-S.3	I was absorbed in this experience	I was absorbed in this experience	Kelly was absorbed in this experience
Perceived Usability (PU)			
PU-S.1	I felt frustrated while using this Application X	I felt frustrated while using this VR application	Kelly felt frustrated while using this VR application
PU-S.2	I found this Application X confusing to use	I found this VR application confusing to use	Kelly found this VR application confusing to use
PU-S.3	Using this Application X was taxing	Using this VR application was taxing	Using this VR application was taxing
Aesthetic Elements (AE)			
AE-S.1	This Application X was attractive	This VR application was attractive	This VR application was attractive
AE-S.2	This Application X was aesthetically appealing	This VR application was aesthetically appealing	This VR application was aesthetically appealing
AE-S.3	Application X appealed to my visual senses	The VR application appealed to my visual senses	The VR application appealed to Kelly's visual senses
Reward Factor (RW)			
RW-S.1	Using Application X was worthwhile	Using the VR application was worthwhile	Using the VR application was worthwhile
RW-S.2	My experience was rewarding	My experience was rewarding	Kelly's experience was rewarding
RW-S.3	I felt interested in this experience	I felt interested in this experience	Kelly felt interested in this experience

Table A2: PCY items: original version, post-VR adaptation, and post-Alex adaptation.

ID	Original version	Post-VR adaptation	Post-Alex adaptation
Perceived Cybersecurity Risks (PCY)			
PCY1	I am concerned that [product] collects too much personal information about me	I am concerned that this VR application collects too much personal information about me	I am concerned that this VR application collects too much personal information
PCY2	I am concerned that my personal information may be given or sold to others without my consent when I use [product]	I am concerned that my personal information may be given or sold to others without my consent when I use this VR application	I am concerned that my personal information may be given or sold to others without my consent when I use this VR application
PCY3	I am concerned that [product] can be hacked by cybercriminals through potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities	I am concerned that this VR application can be hacked by cybercriminals through potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities	I am concerned that this VR application can be hacked by cybercriminals through potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities
PCY4	I believe that the use of [product] is dangerous because of the potential for cyberattacks	I believe that the use of this VR application is dangerous because of the potential for cyberattacks	I believe that the use of this VR application is dangerous because of the potential for cyberattacks

1 Alex receives an email from Carrefour's HR department inviting him to a virtual job interview.

2 To attend the interview, he must download and install a VR application.

3 Before starting, he puts on his headset, reads a consent text, and clicks "Accept".

4 Alex attends his virtual interview with the recruiter.

5 After a few checks and adjustments, the interview begins.

6 The interview concludes. Alex will receive the outcome of his application within 15 days.

7 Two weeks later, his application is rejected.

8 Unbeknownst to him, biometric profiling of his micro-expressions shaped it.

Figure A3: Storyboard panels of Alex's biometric profiling scenario (Study 2). Images generated using DALLÉ 3 and ChatGPT.

1

On the first day of her internship, Kelly learns that virtual reality is central to the company's working methods.

2

Putting on her VR headset, Kelly sees a dashboard with daily objectives, points, and rankings.

3

Later that day, Kelly checks the VR ranking on a big screen. The top performer earns a golden badge each month.

4

Kelly keeps her headset on to chase points. The fleeting thrill leaves her more absorbed in VR and less connected to others.

5

With each task, she earns points. Euphoria rises, fades quickly, driving her to complete more tasks.

6

Two weeks later, Kelly reaches the top five, but it's not enough; another intern stays ahead.

7

After a month of intense effort, Kelly sets a task record and receives a virtual gold badge.

8

On the last day of their internship, the trainees celebrate. Kelly has not built connections and is not invited.

Figure A4: Storyboard panels of Kelly's overengagement scenario (Study 2). Images generated using DALLÉ 3 and ChatGPT.